

TRIBOLOGICAL BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COPPER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The tribological behavior including the effect of carbon fiber volume content v_f on the coefficient of friction μ , the wear rate W , the constituent of the abrasive piece, the wearing surface and the abrasive mechanism of carbon fiber reinforced copper-5%tin matrix composites prepared by hot pressing had been studied. It is found that μ and W decrease with the increasing of V_f , might be due to the formation of both adhesive wear and oxidative wear under the given condition. However, at high temperature or with large V_f , oxidative abrasion is the main type.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced copper matrix composites with the properties of very low thermal expansion and good conductivity, can be used as semiconductor devices and wear reduction parts(1). We studied the wear and friction behavior of short carbon fiber reinforced copper-5%tin matrix composites under sliding condition in air without adding lubricants, attempting to get the effect of some parameters such as sliding distance and V_f on the tribo-property and the wear mechanism of the composites.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

1. Preparing of specimen

The continuous carbon fibers were electroplated with copper of about $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ thickness as shown in Fig. 1(a), and chopped into about 1mm length. The short fibers were sufficiently mixed with the metal powders(Cu and Sn powders) and was hot pressed in 1028-1033k under 50MPa for 0.5hr. then cut the material into $15 \times 10 \times 3\text{mm}$ for testibg. Fig. 1(b) shows the microstructure of the specimen.

2. Testing procedure

The friction and wear testing were performed in air condition to simulate the severe abrasive process under dry sliding conditions. A surface nitriding 38CrMnAl steel disk of 40mm diameter and 10mm thickness was pressed on the specimen which was fixed on a block. The running disk at a speed of 400rpm. gave a 100N normal pressure on the specimen. Wesr rate was expressed by the weight loss per test load and length of sliding.

RESULTS

We get the relation among the coefficient of friction, the wear rate and carbon fiber

Fig. 1 Optical micrograph of
(a) Cu layer on carbon fibers
(b) CF/Cu-5%Sn composite($v_f=30\%$)

volume fraction as shown in Fig. 2. The matrix Cu-5%Sn without carbon fiber has a bigger μ than CF/Cu-5%Sn composites when contacted with 38CrMnAl steel disk. The frictional coefficients of the composites monotonously decrease with the increasing of carbon fiber volume content. When the sliding length keeps constant, the composite with higher V_f has a lower wear rate, which agrees with reference (2). The wear rate of the composites with $V_f=50\%$ and 20% in different sliding distance are given in Fig. 3. The curves shown can be divided into three stages. When the disk is just touched with the specimens, the wear rates are very low (the first stage); then the wear rates increase rapidly (the second stage). After a period of time ($n \geq 2 \times 10^4$), the curves become flat and the wear rates keep constant (the third stage).

Small pieces (less than $10 \mu\text{m}$) were generated from the composites during sliding. Some of the pieces stay on the abraded surface. Chemical analysis of pieces collected from the wear surface showed that it consists of copper oxide, carbon and less Cu powder. Composite with higher V_f (e.g., $V_f=50\%$) generated more copper oxide pieces and less Cu powder explains the predominant abrasion cause is oxidization of the surface, whereas the low fiber content composite ($V_f=20\%$) produced much more Cu powder explains the main cause is plastical deformation of the sliding surface. Fig. 4, the micrograph of the wear surface of the composite with $V_f=50\%$, shows that a coarse surface generated by the surface film breaking and some abraded pieces still remained on it.

Fig. 2 The effect of V_f on (a) the coefficient of friction (b) wear rate

Fig. 3 The sliding wear rates of the composites in different friction length.

Fig. 4 SEM micrograph of the abraded surface of the composite with $V_f=50\%$

DISCUSSION

When the specimen of Cu-5%Sn alloy containing no fiber was pressed on the steel disk and sliding, there were point contact on the wear surface and yielded cold-welding or adhesion with each other due to plastic deformation the adhesion and plough forces strongly resist the relative motion between the frictional couple. Thus, high coefficient of friction appears for sliding. The adhesive area was hardened after several deformation. Defect, dislocation accumulated beneath the hardening layer, cracks initiated in the faulty domain and propagated in the following wear processes. Finally, the hardened layer was broken and peeled into pieces, causing material removal off the sliding portion severely. The CF/Cu-5%Sn and 38CrMnAl steel frictional couple partly produces cold-welding, whereas other contacting parts exhibit protruded fibers and plastic deformation still exists in the range of B shown in Fig. 5.

Because of the reinforcement of the fiber, the contact area of the specimen deforms more difficult than the specimen of Cu-5%Sn. The deformed layer is thinner and not easily cold-welded as Cu-5%Sn alloy. Thus, CF/Cu-5%Sn composite has a lower coefficient of friction. During sliding, carbon fibers protruded on the surface shear to pieces and form a tribolayered graphite film (3), which decreases the fric-

tional coefficient further. The thin deformed layer in adhesive area helps to prompt the abrasive resistance, since thinner layer consisting of little pieces of abrasive products has more surface energy, the composites can absorb more frictional energy as indicated by the theory of frictional energy conversion, and little pieces have a weak ploughing and cutting effect as well.(4)

Except the formation of stain energy due to plastic deformation in contacting area and the surface energy of the wear pieces, the total frictional energy can convert into thermal energy. Thus, the frictional couple were heated and the abraded surface oxidized. Oxide layer broken and peeled, formed a very important part of the abrasion products. This consideration may be convinced by the analysis of the abraded pieces, which contain copper oxide.

As mentioned above, not only adhesion but also oxidization occurred during the sliding process leads the wear of CF/Cu-5%sn. With different V_f , the two abrasive products have different relative proportions. When V_f is low (e.g. $V_f=20\%$), the wear formed by adhesion is dominant. Fig.6 indicates such a typical adhesive abrasion character. Wear stages remain on the surface of the specimen attributing to the flaking of larger abrasive pieces much different from the view of Fig.4. With higher V_f , and thus with a weak adhesion and thin deformed layer on specimen, the amount of adhesive wear decreases, while a mild oxidative wear is the main form.

Fig. 5 A schematic drawing illustrating the contact of the frictional couple
 A: area of cold-welding
 B: no cold-welding area
 C: carbon fibers

Fig. 6 SEM micrograph of the composite with $v_f=20\%$

when the temperature during sliding raised above 623K, detected by a thermocouple placed near the wear surface, the composites behave good property of anti-abrasion, owing to its special tribological behavior. Once the thickness of oxidized layer (Cu_2O , Cu_2O_2) is going up to $0.75 \mu m$, the coefficient of friction will increase dramatically to 0.79-1.21(5), but carbon fibers as a lubricant can improve the tribo-condition and inhibit oxidization further, From the theory of metal oxidization, oxidizing can be considered as the result of the electrochemical reaction in the corrosion cell which contains a oxide solid electrolyte(6). In CF/Cu-5%Su composites, the main oxidizative-reductive galvanic couples may exist as follows:

and induce a series reactions(7). Oxygen was reduced into $O^-, O^=$ in the edge outside the oxide layer. While beneath the layer, Cu was oxidized into Cu^+, Cu^{++} . The layer is growing thicker and thicker by the inter-diffusion of Cu^+, Cu^{++} and $O^-, O^=$ through defects in the oxide film. The dynamic process of oxidization can be slowed down by the fibers which can adsorb $O^-, O^=$ due to the inherent porosity on the surface having a

stronger affinity with oxygen than the matrix.

At higher temperature, carbon has a stronger inclination to oxidize than that of Cu, so the sacrificial oxidization of C can protect Cu keeping from oxidizing, since:

took place, and led the abraded surface lack of oxygen, moreover, the product CO has a strong ability of reduction, the oxidizing of Cu was inhibited further. Therefore, continuous oxide film can not be erected on the surface. Discontinuous layer broken into little pieces during wear resulting a low abrasive wear rate.

CONCLUSION

1. The carbon fiber reinforced Cu-5%Sn composite has a smaller coefficient of friction and lower abrasive wear rate than Cu-5%Sn alloy.
2. The coefficient of friction and the wear rate of CF/Cu-5%Sn decrease with the increasing of carbon fiber volume content.
3. with a low V_f , the adhesive abrasion is the main form, while for high V_f composites, the oxidative wear is dominant.
4. CF/Cu-5%Sn composite material has a good property of wear-resistant because of its special tribological behavior. It can be used as the material for wear reduction parts working at high temperature.

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